

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT AND CONTENT OF INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION IN RUMI'S LEGACY

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Abstract

The article examines the issue of intellectual education in the works of Jalaluddin Rumi. It notes that Rumi paid special attention to the intellect and intellectual development, elevating its importance in human life. The article emphasizes that intellect is a feature of human psychology and a product of the brain. According to the researcher's classification, Rumi, who approached intellect as a divine force, considered it essential to apply reason in resolving social and political matters, presenting intellectual development as an inseparable part of heredity and education. The author notes that in Rumi's works, based on the essence of the concept of intellect, the content, functions, and practical methods of intellectual education are clearly defined. As mentioned, Rumi called those who do not recognize or are unwilling to recognize their faults foolish, ignorant, or unlearned. Furthermore, the article analyzes and evaluates Rumi's views on family relationships, preparation for family life, establishing a family, strengthening it, and preserving it, in the context of modern pedagogical requirements.

Keywords: Rumi; concept of intellect; family; intellect and heredity; moral development

In academic pedagogy, the development of intellect is studied both in the didactic section and in the section on educational theory. This is because through the development of intellect a person can achieve success in life. By means of intellect, one is able to distinguish good from evil. In our holy book, the Qur'an, there are 49 verses that command people to act with reason, 18 verses that praise and commend those who possess intellect, and 31 verses that speak about the necessity of reflecting and drawing lessons through the power of reason. Even before creating the universe with the command "Be!" (Kun!), God had conceived of the Human being and decreed that the universe would be created for humankind. God bestowed the universe as a gift in honor of the Human. The Moon, the Sun, all the planets, and all blessings were created to serve humankind. Therefore, the Human may be called the cherished child of nature. In the fourth verse of Surah At-Tin of the Holy Qur'an it is said: "We have certainly created man in the best form." [1, p.636]. For this reason, since the human being is the most perfect among all creations, he or she should be noble, benevolent, and humanistic, and must always be aware of his or her responsibility and accountability before all beings that stand at a lower level. The Human is obliged to love, protect, and sustain the entire world of flora and fauna, and all of nature. One of the principal virtues of humankind should be to perfect society and to establish an organic harmony between nature and society. When God was distributing light (the Eternal Light) to the universe, to nature, and to humanity, He granted a greater share of that essence or light to the Human being. And humankind has benefited more from this essence. For unlike other living creatures, the human being has been endowed with the power of intellect. Alongside this, not only spiritual superiority and the unparalleled gift called intellect were bestowed upon the human being, but also physical superiority was granted. For this reason, the human is regarded as the king of living beings,

and responsibility for all creation rests upon his shoulders. One may ask: why has such exceptional importance been given to reason since the very day human society came into existence? An answer to this question can be found in Mawlana Jalal al-Din Rumi's extensive work, the *Masnawi*. "O father! Even if you possess intellect, befriend another intellect and consult with it. With two intellects you will be saved from many troubles and place your foot upon the heights of the heavens" [2, 438] — said Jalal al-Din Rumi, who regarded intellect as a sublime power.

Prominent Azerbaijani psychologists Akbar Bayramov and Abdul Alizade, in their textbook *Psychology*, group the qualities of the intellect as follows:

- Independence of intellect;
- Criticality of intellect;
- Depth of intellect;
- Flexibility of intellect;
- Independence of thought. [3, 355].

Naturally, these listed qualities are inseparable components of one another and are closely interconnected. Relying on such qualities reflected in Mawlana's views on the cultivation of intellect, we would like to interpret certain problems of cognition.

First of all, when we look at Jalal al-Din Rumi's creativity, we see that, based on his own knowledge and experience, he thought independently, set new goals, questions, and problems without assistance from others, found means and methods to answer questions accepted by humanity and to solve issues or problems in order to achieve his aims, and arrived at definite conclusions. He was an incomparable master in expressing judgments, ideas, and opinions about the causes that give rise to objects and phenomena. In this sense, Jalal al-Din Rumi, the possessor of boundless intellect, expressed highly significant ideas concerning the education of the mind, made generalizations, and clearly and vividly articulated the characteristics of intellect.

Jalal al-Din Rumi, likening knowledge to an inexhaustible treasure and intellect to a garment that neither wears out nor grows old—as in the example of Ali ibn Abi Talib, a sacred figure of our religion and faith—divided intellect into two types [4, 44]: innate intellect and intellect acquired through hearing and life experience. When a person receives education, he learns by listening to the teacher; this is heard (or acquired) knowledge—and thus acquired intellect. However, a person must also possess an innate talent, a natural ability, in order to understand what he hears; this is natural knowledge (or intellect). Mawlana calls natural knowledge a gift from the Truth (God). He notes that without natural knowledge, acquired knowledge is of no benefit—that is, if a person lacks the capacity for comprehension, the knowledge he hears will yield no benefit. He substantiates his view as follows: “Intellect is of two kinds: The first is acquired—you learn like a child at school, from book, teacher, reflection, and remembrance, from meanings and from fine new knowledge. Your intellect becomes superior to that of others, yet you struggle to preserve it. As you wander, you become like a guarded tablet; The one who transcends this is the Preserved Tablet (Lawh al-Mahfuz). The other intellect is the gift of the Truth; Its fountain lies in the midst of the soul. When the river of knowledge gushes from the heart, it neither decays, nor turns sour, nor fades. If the path to its source is blocked, what sorrow can there be? For at every moment it boils and flows from within the house. The intellect acquired through study is like streams that flow to a house from the streets; When the waterway is cut off, it becomes poor— Seek the fountain from within yourself.” [2, 485].

Rumi, who is capable of creative thought, amazes his readers with new ideas, new words, and profound reflections. Do Rumi’s thought-provoking and delightful ideas not reveal the depth of his mind to the reader? By providing sufficiently consistent evidence for his judgments, does he not derive beauty from each successive thought based on the previous one? Just as the universe is infinite, so is the process of understanding it; one could say that Rumi’s intellect and contemplation are always directed toward the endless depths of novelty. Rumi writes that a philosopher is connected to what is appropriate for the mind. The essence belongs to the intellect, while the intellect itself is its shell. The stomach of an animal constantly seeks shells. One who seeks the essence is weary of the shell a hundred times over. “The essence is lawful for noble people. Even if the shell of the mind provides a hundred proofs, how can all-encompassing intellect take a step without precise belief? The intellect fills entire notebooks; the intellect has moonlit horizons. It has no relation to darkness or light; its moon-lover, heart, and soul illuminate.”

Jalaluddin Rumi does not view those who lack benevolent thoughts as wise people and asserts with certainty that such individuals can never triumph over intellect and light. For “intellect is luminous and desires the good; so how can the soul, which belongs to darkness, overcome it?” [2, p. 196]. Everyone must first be able to perceive the outcome in every action they un-

dertake. Rumi calls such people “sharp-sighted.” A person who can clearly imagine that an action will lead to a good outcome before starting it demonstrates competence, which indicates that they are wise. Conversely, one who cannot foresee the result of their actions is considered foolish, ignorant, or unlearned, Rumi writes: “A wise person sees the end of the action beforehand with their heart. The ignorant person sees it only in the end” [2, p.253]. Or: “A child’s vision is like manure on a donkey, while the wise person’s sight is on the final account” [2,p. 278]. He also states: “The wise are sharp-sighted. God allows them to draw from His guidance so that they may see ahead” [2, p.335].

Jalaluddin Rumi also notes that intellect and consciousness should not be equated. From children to adults, everyone possesses consciousness, but it is not correct to consider everyone wise. A truly wise person is regarded as a sage. Their hair may turn white, yet their mind may not carry greatness. “Wisdom comes with age, not with white hair. Luck and hope cannot contain a single hair” [2, p.177]. As seen, in his works, Rumi emphasizes the essence of intellect and focuses on clarifying the content [5], duties, and methods of intellectual cultivation. He calls those who do not recognize their faults or are unwilling to see them foolish, ignorant, or unlearned. Even if such people attempt to instill good traits in friendship, companionship, kinship, or society, they only cause harm and damage. Rumi urges his readers to avoid such individuals, conveying this advice through the words of the wise and insightful Prophet Jesus : “I recited the prayer and the most exalted Name to darkness, and it improved. I recited it to a mountain of stone; it split, tearing its rock to the sky. I recited it over a dead body, and life returned. I recited it over nothingness, and something came into being. But I recited it to the heart of a fool with love a hundred thousand times, and there was no healing. Avoid fools as Jesus avoided them. Being with a fool has spilled much blood” [2, 198]. Rumi, the herald of humanism, believes that such people can never attain happiness. He considers doing good for the foolish not an act of kindness but of malice, opposing abstract benevolence. He writes: “Tie the hand of one who has weapons but lacks intellect, lest they cause a hundredfold harm” [2, 449]. As we leaf through Jalaluddin Rumi’s *Masnavi*, one thing becomes clear: Rumi placed great importance on heredity alongside education in the formation of personality, sometimes even considering heredity as primary. He viewed it as a factor passed down from generation to generation, or from predecessors to successors. Attempting to explain the traits of human character from the perspective of heredity, Rumi emphasizes that the features of character are the result of inherited qualities. That is, heredity plays a role in the formation of moral, physical, and intellectual attributes, as well as in the transmission of outward characteristics.

Rumi writes: “O great man! It is better not to know your foundational sciences than to ignore two fundamental sciences – jurisprudence (fiqh) and theology (kalam)” [2, p. 202]. Likewise, he says: “Teaching knowledge and science to a man without lineage is like giving a sword to a highway robber” [2, p. 449]. Rumi, who likens the intellect to the garment of knowledge,

presents the principle that “a person’s intellect must govern their emotions.” This should be understood to mean that since human emotions arise from the impact of external events and circumstances on one’s feelings, the intellect must determine which emotions are good, which are bad, correct the bad, and cultivate the good. If a person’s emotions (feelings, imagination, etc.) do not obey the intellect, if the intellect does not free the person from the domination of negative emotions, and if it does not protect them from becoming a slave to their passions, then behavior is guided not by reason but by instincts, making it difficult to distinguish a human from an animal.

Rumi refers to such intellect in common terms as “partial intellect,” not the intellect capable of judgment, and he asks rhetorically: “How far can the aimless path of intellect and feeling go? Partial intellect is not the intellect that can judge; it is only capable of receiving knowledge” [2, p. 440]. In other words, if a wise person can control their emotions, their ability to “govern themselves” is elevated. From Rumi’s pedagogical perspective, most failures occur because people are unable to properly manage their own emotions and passions. Thus, Jalaluddin Rumi sought to clarify the essence of intellectual education and to highlight its characteristic features.

In Jalaluddin Rumi’s works, while discussing family and love, he also emphasizes the value of intellect and highly esteems a family built on reason. Rumi writes that a family is a union based on mutual love, trust, faith, and respect—formed through the interaction of a husband and wife whose moral convictions and worldview are well developed. Such a union brings about the beginning of a new life, the birth of a new generation, and assumes the responsibility for its upbringing. Rumi regards the father and mother as the core and primary unit of society. Valuing parental relationships highly, he refers to the father as the “sky” and the mother as the “earth,” highlighting their fundamental and complementary roles: “According to intellect, the sky represents the man and the earth represents the woman; it nurtures what the man sows. When heat is

absent, it gives warmth; when moisture and dampness are gone, it provides them. The earth takes on the role of homemaker, overseeing childbirth and nursing. Therefore, know the earth and the sky by intellect, for they fulfill the work of the wise” [2, p.323]. Although Rumi did not conduct systematic research on family, he interpreted issues such as preparation for family life, establishing a family, strengthening it, and preserving it as the foundation of society according to his worldview. (For example: How does one understand preparation for family life? What conditions are necessary for forming a family? And so on.)

In conclusion, Jalaluddin Rumi, who considered the ability to grasp the subtlety of events as the highest intellectual quality, has achieved immortality in the world through his rational insights. If parents in the modern era use Rumi’s wisdom as a valuable tool to develop their children’s intellect, it will surely contribute to their success. Through his exceptional creativity, Rumi demonstrated the value of intellect and simultaneously criticized qualities contrary to it. Even as years and centuries pass, his aphorisms and wise sayings about intellect continue to nourish and will continue to nourish the human mind in both essence and character.

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